

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RESULTS OF VARIOUS SURGICAL PROCEDURES
PERFORMED FOR PORTAL HYPERTENSION DUE TO
HEPATOPORTAL SCLEROSIS (NONCIRRHOTIC PORTAL
FIBROSIS)****Dr. Mazia Shabbir¹, Dr. Raana Shahid², Dr. Tehrim Tahir³**
^{1,2,3} House Officers at Sir Ganga Ram hospital, Lahore**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Hepatoportal sclerosis or idiopathic portal hypertension is widespread worldwide in developing and temperate countries.

Goal: *The aim of the study was determine the outcomes of various surgical procedures for portal hypertension due to hepatoportal sclerosis.*

Place and Duration: *For 3-years duration from October 2016 to September 2019, in the Surgical department of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore.*

Methods: *Data for three years was collected in which Splenectomy or Shunt surgery was performed in 30 of 46 patients in three years duration. Indications for surgical intervention were severe hypersplenism and persistent upper left abdominal pain or frequent esophageal bleeding. Two operational deaths were due to uncontrolled bleeding.*

Results: *None of the 30 patients experienced esophageal bleeding or encephalopathy for 1 to 3 years. Splenectomy was effective in patients without bleeding. The proximal splenorenal shunt is also satisfactory in all cases. In recent cases, however, Warren's shunt has brought even more encouraging results.*

Conclusion: *In addition to the general definition, the features of this disease, which were not previously discussed or highlighted in the literature, were presented in long-term results along with the surgical results and the surgical methods used.*

Key words: *hepatoportal sclerosis, portal hypertension, surgical experience.*

Corresponding author:**Mazia Shabbir,**

House Officers at Sir Ganga Ram hospital, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Mazia Shabbir et al., **Results Of Various Surgical Procedures Performed For Portal Hypertension Due To Hepatoportal Sclerosis (Noncirrhotic Portal Fibrosis)**., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Portal hypertension in the absence of liver cirrhosis or other apparent mechanical obstruction has been a worrying syndrome since Banti et. al¹⁻². Although this syndrome was reported and discussed sporadically before 1965 / "Mikkelsen et al. Since then, several researchers in Pakistan, Europe and Japan have done a lot to further clarify the clinical-pathological features of this disease and clearly distinguish it from various forms of liver cirrhosis³⁻⁴. The main features of this disease include mainly moderate to huge spleen, with esophageal varices and sometimes well-tolerated bleeding episodes, and anemia with secondary hypersplenism and portal hypertension. Liver function tests are normal or slightly abnormal⁵. There should be no evidence of liver cirrhosis in general examination and liver microscopy. This disease has been identified in the literature under various names such as hepatportal sclerosis, cirrhosis without portal fibrosis and idiopathic portal hypertension⁶. Of course, by definition, there should be no other known causes of the hypertensive portal such as: parasites, tumor, blood disease, macroscopic thrombosis or extra hepatic obstruction or obvious portal arterio-venous fistula.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held for 3-years duration from October 2016 to September 2019, in the Surgical department of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Lahore. 30 patients who met the criteria of idiopathic portal hypertension (IPH) were operated on. A study was conducted to compare the clinical and laboratory characteristics of this disease with cirrhosis and to assess the prevalence of IPH in our patient population. To this end, records of all portal hypertension with and without cirrhosis were reviewed over a three-year period.

The criteria used to determine the diagnosis of IPH in patients are described by Nayak et al., "Anthony et al." And Okuda et al. However, we removed from our series all patients who were positive for HBsAg. All patients previously had a detailed medical history and physical examination with particular emphasis on their disease. All patients underwent blood and liver function tests, and endoscopic esophagoscopy. The patient underwent bone marrow aspiration, liver needle biopsy. In addition to routine hematoxylin and eosin, the samples were stained with silver impregnation for reticulin fibers and trichrome for collagen. The previously

scheduled intraoperative examination exempted from all patients included liver and spleen examination and abundant right wedge lobe biopsies. Portal pressure routinely calculated from the jejunum vein. The maxillary artery was temporarily ligated to determine the effect of its portal pressure ligation. Portal pressure was measured again at the end of the operation.

RESULTS:

In our series, 50 patients with IPH were evaluated. 30 patients were operated, therefore open liver biopsy and intraoperative portal pressure measurements were performed. The remaining cases were selected on the basis of clinical needle biopsies and the results of clinical and laboratory tests. The incidence of IPH (compared to cirrhosis) in our patient population was 12 percent. The main symptoms in these patients were: upper quarter pain, discomfort, easy fatigue, inability to work hard and a hematoma. Two findings deserve to be highlighted in patient stories. First, many patients have had a "fever" disease in the past and some of them have had diarrhea. No one had any idea about the nature of this fever. Secondly, 20 patients (76%), 26 of whom were asked about the history of Pica presence, accepted this habit when they were children or adolescents. Some admitted that it lasted until late puberty, and one patient was used to 25 years of age. There was no detailed information on the amount and frequency of clay or plaster consumption because patients often did not want to fully discuss this problem or were embarrassed. 90% of patients came from small towns or villages. For physical examination; apparently no patient was malnourished, but the majority had anemia and seemed weak. Six young patients (aged 15-20) exhibited growth retardation and delayed secondary sexual development. One patient in the whole group did not show cirrhosis or clear acid stigmata. Subcutaneous abdominal-motor venous security was not minimal. There were 30 men and 20 women. The age distribution of patients is shown in Table I.

IPH patients, Age and Sex distribution are given in Table-1

Age group in Years	Male	Female
0-10	0	0
11-20	17	5
21-30	5	8
31-40	3	2
41-50	4	4
Above 50	1	1
Total	30	20

The frequency of the most obvious clinical findings is shown in Table II. Laboratory tests showed anemia and panic, except for abnormal liver function tests and clear and continuous abnormal prothrombin time. Hemoglobin values range from 7 g/dl to 13.5 g/dl (average 9.6 g/dl).

Clinical features are given in Table-II

Clinical findings	Patients percentage
Left-sided abdominal pain	65%
Splenomegaly	95%
History of Hematemesis	40%
Esophageal varices on barium meal	48%
Ascites	25%
Palpable Liver	30%

The number of white blood cells dropped in 50% of cases, but was never less than 2,500. Platelet counts ranged from 60,000 to 300,000, with an average of 120,000. Bilirubin values were within normal limits in 75% of patients, and in cases where the value was high, never exceeding 2.5 mg/100 ml. Serum electrophoresis showed an increase in alpha₂ globulin (60%), beta₂ globulin (50%) and gammaglobulin (80%). Many patients had mild to moderate decreases in serum albumin, but this value never fell below 2.8 g/dl. Of the liver function tests, the longest result is an increase in prothrombin time. In three patients it was only 12 seconds (control: 12 seconds). All liver and open needle biopsies were consistent with the diagnosis of portal cirrhosis without cirrhosis. In some cases, the fibrosis is concentric in the portal areas, and in others the fibrosis extends to the parenchyma, but does not bind to adjacent portal areas, forming nodules. In many cases, mild and moderate mononuclear cells were infiltrated in portal areas. Surgical procedure, 30 patients were operated on. After operative portal pressure readings and temporary interruption of the splenic artery flow, the presence or absence of a history of hematemesis, splenectomy itself, or fistula procedure was performed. Only splenectomy was performed in patients with no history of upper gastrointestinal bleeding or after the splenic artery fell below 20 cm, otherwise a transfusion procedure was performed. The types of operations performed are shown in Table III.

Types of Operations performed in 30 patients given in Table 3

Operation Type	No of patients
Proximal splenorenal shunt	09
Splenectomy	16
Mesocaval (H-graft)	02
Distalsplenorenal (Warren's)	02
Portocaval	01

The first intraoperative portal pressure values are shown in Table IV. The mean decrease in portal pressure after spleen artery binding was 10.7 cm of normal saline, and the mean decrease in portal pressure after bypass procedures was 16.3 in normal saline. The explanation of the abdominal results is extraordinary. The liver was not always smooth and spheroidal, but because of the increase in fibrosis it was tighter than usual with gray-white dye. Spleen is large to large with a solid consistency and a thick capsule. In many patients, the spleen is particularly attached to the diaphragm and adjacent guts due to tight adhesions (perisplenic inflammation). Through these lineo-renal and gastro-spleen ligaments, in any case, wide dilated and curved vessels rushed to protect the diaphragm and upper abdomen. In many cases, findings in the upper left abdomen suggest that inflammation in the spleen was present at some point in the past. The spleen usually reveals areas of thickening and thinning. In recent cases, we have performed routine biopsies of the spleen vein and confirmed the pathology wall and thickening of the intima (phlebitis). The spleen artery is in most cases very large, enlarged and curved.

Portal pressure in 30 patients given in Table 4

Portal pressure in cm normal saline	No of Patients
Less than 19	0
20-29	12
30-39	14
Above 40	4

The planned splenectomy was performed in 16 cases in the splenectomy group. In three patients, the planned bypass operation was abandoned due to difficult splenectomy due to the full adhesion of the spleen to the diaphragm and continuous blood

exudate, which required considerable time and effort to control it. The portasystemic shunt was used in 9 patients (Table III). In recent cases, the splenic artery was ligated. In these patients, the spleen size decreased and the hematological abnormalities improved. Four referrals were made in four patients due to insufficient spleen vessels. Three patients had one H transplant and the mesenteric vein was not ideal in either case. With the exception of operative death, all patients coped very well with anemia and reduced LUQ pain after surgery. One patient in group H with transplantation had postoperative hematemesis due to graft thrombosis.

DISCUSSION:

Although the etiology and pathogenesis of IPH remains unclear, much is known about its pathological stigma⁷⁻⁸. Our patients are pathologically quite similar to those reported from the USA, "England" and India. But they are more similar to those reported clinically from northern India. Although pathological continuations appear to be the same worldwide, disturbing factors may be different. The main pathological change is fibrosis and such liver sclerosis⁹⁻¹⁰. However, in some of our patients, spleen morphology does not reflect simple passive obstruction. Based on their experience in injection and corrosion techniques, Boyer and colleagues believe that the underlying pathology is the thrombotic occlusion of the end-hepatic portal vein branches¹¹⁻¹². Currently, however, the clinical-pathological criteria for the diagnosis of this disease include portal hypertension and splenomegaly with hepatic fibrosis without cirrhosis or other known causes. There seems to be uncertainty and overlap of IPH with tropical spleen syndrome. As for proper treatment and the natural history of this disease, much less is written in the literature¹³. We examined three patients after eight, nine and 12 years. Physical conditions were good and liver function tests remained unchanged, and repeated needle liver biopsy showed perinatal fibrosis again without evidence of cirrhosis. Many patients who were examined one to six years after the surgery recovered and had no discomfort. It is interesting that none of our operated patients developed postoperative esophageal bleeding or encephalopathy more than 13 years ago since our first surgery in these patients. Zeegan et al. Similar results were achieved. There is no observation in patients without surgery¹⁴. In patients without a frequent and severe history of hematemesis, splenectomy is an effective procedure, and long-

term studies have confirmed this result. But the bypass procedure is generally preferred. Warren's recovery seems to be a particularly effective procedure. These patients did not develop postoperative pain or fever. The spleen size was significantly reduced, and the hematological profile later improved.

REFERENCES:

1. Fiel, M.I. and Schiano, T.D., 2019, July. Idiopathic noncirrhotic portal hypertension. In *Seminars in diagnostic pathology*. WB Saunders.
2. Freiberg, B., Emre, S., Morotti, R., Dillon, B., Koral, A., Hattangadi, S.M. and Valentino, P.L., 2019. Progressive Splenomegaly and Hypersplenism: An Unusual Case of Splenic Vein Stenosis with Histologic Findings of Hepatoportal Sclerosis. *The Journal of Pediatrics*.
3. Matsutani, S., 2019. Idiopathic Portal Hypertension. In *Clinical Investigation of Portal Hypertension* (pp. 549-557). Springer, Singapore.
4. Slowik, V., Monroe, E.J., Friedman, S.D., Hsu, E.K. and Horslen, S., 2019. Pressure gradients, laboratory changes, and outcomes with transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunts in pediatric portal hypertension. *Pediatric transplantation*, 23(3), p.e13387.
5. Guido, M., Alves, V.A., Balabaud, C., Bathal, P.S., Bioulac-Sage, P., Colombari, R., Crawford, J.M., Dhillon, A.P., Ferrell, L.D., Gill, R.M. and Hytiroglou, P., 2019. Histology of portal vascular changes associated with idiopathic non-cirrhotic portal hypertension: nomenclature and definition. *Histopathology*, 74(2), pp.219-226.
6. Kumar, S. and Chandra, A., 2019. Noncirrhotic Portal Fibrosis in a Young Girl. *Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition*, 68(3), p.e51.
7. Goel, A., Ramakrishna, B., Zachariah, U., Sajith, K.G., Burad, D.K., Kodiatte, T.A., Keshava, S.N., Balasubramanian, K.A., Elias, E. and Eapen, C.E., 2019. What makes non-cirrhotic portal hypertension a common disease in India? Analysis for environmental factors. *The Indian journal of medical research*, 149(4), p.468.
8. Puente, A., Fortea, J.I., Del Pozo, C., Huelin, P., Cagigal, M.L., Serrano, M., Cabezas, J., Arias Lose, M.T., Iruzubieta, P., Cuadrado, A. and

- Llerena, S., 2019. Porto-Sinusoidal Vascular Disease Associated to Oxaliplatin: An Entity to Think about It. *Cells*, 8(12), p.1506.
9. Berendse, K., Koot, B.G., Klouwer, F.C., Engelen, M., Roels, F., Lacle, M.M., Nikkels, P.G., Verheij, J. and Poll-The, B.T., 2019. Hepatic symptoms and histology in 13 patients with a Zellweger spectrum disorder. *Journal of inherited metabolic disease*, 42(5), pp.955-965.
 10. Khanna, R. and Sarin, S.K., 2019. Noncirrhotic Portal Hypertension: Current and Emerging Perspectives. *Clinics in Liver Disease*, 23(4), pp.781-807.
 11. Navin, P.J., Gidener, T., Allen, A.M., Yin, M., Takahashi, N., Torbenson, M.S., Kamath, P.S., Ehman, R.L. and Venkatesh, S.K., 2019. The role of magnetic resonance elastography in the diagnosis of noncirrhotic portal hypertension. *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*.
 12. Chouraqui, E., Leguilloux, L., Dohan, A., Gouya, H., Barral, M., Vallet-Pichard, A., Sogni, P., Pol, S., Mallet, V. and Soyer, P., 2020. Can we differentiate HIV-associated obliterative portopathy from liver cirrhosis using MRI?. *European radiology*, 30(1), pp.213-223.
 13. Mohamed, M.S., Bassiony, M.A. and Mohamed, A.F.E., 2019. The role of mean platelet volume in predicting severity and prognosis of liver cirrhosis in Egyptian patients. *The Egyptian Journal of Internal Medicine*, 31(3), p.261.
 14. Sakamoto, Y., Sakai, M., Sato, K. and Watari, T., 2019. Plasma renin activity and aldosterone concentration in dogs with acquired portosystemic collaterals. *Journal of veterinary internal medicine*.
 15. Elkrief, L., Ferrusquia-Acosta, J., Payancé, A., Moga, L., Tellez, L., Praktijnjo, M., Procopet, B., Farcau, O., De Lédinghen, V., Yuldashev, R. and Tabchouri, N., 2019. Abdominal surgery in patients with idiopathic noncirrhotic portal hypertension: a multicenter retrospective study. *Hepatology*, 70(3), pp.911-924.